

Pyrolysis Oil Upgrading: Electrochemical decarboxylation of carboxylic acids from an applied and fundamental standpoint

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Abstract

Electrochemical upgrading of pyrolysis oil by electro-decarboxylation is an attractive pathway because of near ambient operating conditions, minimal risk and its potential to produce hydrocarbons and hydrogen. Considering that GC-MS results highlight that the major fraction of pyrolysis oil is composed of carboxylic acids and sugars, we first used acetic acid as the model compound. Here, decarboxylation on platinum and BDD electrodes resulted in high faradaic efficiency to ethane (92% on Pt) or methanol (82.3% on BDD), respectively. Using the aqueous phase (50 wt.%) of pyrolysis oil only, we afterwards report the semi-quantitative NMR analysis of treated oil. Contrasting the results obtained with acidic acid using electrolysis with boron-doped diamond (BDD) and Pt electrodes at moderated current density of 25 mA/cm², we show that electrochemical treatment primarily results in an increase in alcohol functional groups. Yet the complexity of the liquid renders more detailed analysis difficult. Thus, it is suggested that the separation of carboxylic acids is essential to achieve electrochemical targeted decarboxylation towards Kolbe or non-Kolbe products, and in general, this study highlights that treating pyrolysis oil is still a major challenge, likely requiring multiple electrochemical processing steps for upgrading.

Keywords: pyrolysis oil, Electrochemical oxidation, decarboxylation, boron-doped diamond electrodes, semi-quantitative NMR analysis.

01. Introduction

The rising energy crises, population growth and environmental challenges, strict policies and carbon taxes open pathways for renewable energy to penetrate the market^{1,2}. To accomplish the energy transition towards renewables, biomass-based feedstocks offer various opportunities to generate chemicals and fuels, thereby creating a circular bioeconomy. The accessibility of biomass sources and their abundance³ makes it an ideal alternative source. Moreover, biomass can be used as a direct/indirect energy source by direct combustion, thermochemical conversion, chemical conversion and biological conversion⁴. Pyrolysis oil can be obtained by

60 thermochemical conversion of biomass/agriculture waste and can provide zero net emissions
61 of CO₂ due to CO₂ recycling via photosynthesis.

62 Pyrolysis oil is a low-value biogenic liquid containing carboxylic acids, sugars, alcohols,
63 ketones, phenolics and lignin compounds. The high amount of oxygenates and low pH causes
64 storage problems and its use in the transportation sector. The energy content of pyrolysis oil is
65 approximately half of fossil-based equivalents⁵ (3.81 MJ/m³ for gasoline and 4.19 MJ/m³ for
66 diesel), which makes it unfeasible to blend into the existing refinery loop and upgrading is
67 required. Conventional methods for pyrolysis oil upgrading are highly energy intensive and
68 require various unit operations. The oxygenates can be converted into other functionalities to
69 increase the energy-density of pyrolysis oil. Though the hydrogenation of pyrolysis oil can
70 improve its quality, it also requires high temperature and pressure (200 °C and up to 200 bar)
71 increasing the overall costs of pyrolysis oil.

72 Electrochemistry might offer an alternative, more efficient approach, particularly as surplus
73 electricity, increasingly available from renewable energy sources, can be utilized to improve
74 bioliquid quality at mild conditions. Moreover, process flexibility allows for reduction and
75 oxidation reactions to proceed at the same time in a paired electrolysis approach further
76 increasing the transformation efficiency. Electrochemical hydrogenation of pyrolysis oil
77 components is widely reported in literature⁶⁻⁸, but electrochemical oxidation being also an
78 appealing route to convert carboxylic acids into alkanes, alcohols and CO₂, thus providing
79 electrons and protons for the cathodic hydrogenation reaction, is less frequently reported.

80 The electrochemical decarboxylation of carboxylic acid was introduced by Michael Faraday in
81 1834. Herman Kolbe showed that acetic acid electrolysis on platinum electrodes yields ethane
82 and CO₂. The so-called Kolbe electrolysis has recently gained attention and product
83 distribution and reaction mechanisms have been analysed. The mechanistic studies show that
84 the coverage of carboxylate on the electrode surface inhibits the oxygen evolution reaction.
85 The electrochemical decarboxylation occurs by the discharge of deprotonated acid (influenced
86 by the electrolyte pH⁹) at potentials $> 2.1 V_{NHE}$, which is critical for forming alkyl radicals that
87 can further react via different reaction pathways yielding products by dimerisation,
88 disproportionation, β -elimination and over oxidation¹⁰. Pt electrodes have been widely used for
89 Kolbe electrolysis¹¹⁻¹⁴ and are considered most effective due to favourable acetate adsorption
90 on the surface¹⁰.

91 Compared to model substrates the direct use of pyrolysis oil has been barely reported in
92 literature. The complexity of pyrolysis oil causes difficulties in the analytics and multiple ex
93 situ techniques are required. In fact the chemical heterogeneity of pyrolysis oil caused by
94 utilization of different bio sources and ageing processes imposes additional challenges with
95 respect to reproducibility of electrochemical performances. Still electrochemically upgrading
96 of pyrolysis oil has been explored, but information on product distribution^{6,7} are lacking and
97 reports frequently only account for the conversion of specific components. In this paper, we
98 first briefly discuss the oxidation of a model compound, acetic acid, on Pt and BDD electrodes
99 before we reveal the complexity and challenges associated with aqueous phase pyrolysis oil
100 oxidation. Specifically using reaction product identification by semi-quantitative 2D-NMR we
101 elaborate on the need for carboxylic acids separation to achieve pyrolysis oil liquids with lower
102 acidity.

103 **02. Materials and Methods**

104 Acetic acid (glacial, ReagentPlus®, ≥99 %, Sigma Aldrich) was chosen as the model
105 compound. The pH of acetic acid electrolyte was adjusted to pH 5 with sodium acetate (ACS
106 reagent, ≥99.0 %, Sigma Aldrich), eliminating the use of additional supporting electrolytes.
107 Before use the electrolyte (acetic acid/sodium acetate, 1M) was purged with helium to remove
108 dissolved oxygen.

109 Pyrolysis oil was produced by a fast pyrolysis process and acquired from BTG, Enschede. The
110 aqueous fraction was prepared by mixing pyrolysis oil with water in equal weight proportion
111 and mixed continuously for 8 hours. The oil/water mixture was placed in a glass bottle for 48
112 hours for phase separation. The aqueous phase was extracted and stained through filter paper
113 with particle retention of 2 - 3 μm. The pH of the pyrolysis liquid was adjusted to 5 by 1M
114 sodium hydroxide solution NaOH(Sigma Aldrich) to facilitate deprotonation of carboxylic
115 acid.

116 Platinum foil (0.025 mm thick, 99.9 % pure, Alfa Aesar) and boron-doped diamond (BDD) on
117 a tantalum substrate (15μm layer on 2mm substrate DIACHEM® - Condias) were used as the
118 working electrode. Platinised/titanium (Magneto Special Anodes B.V.) and Ag/AgCl (3M
119 NaCl ProSense) were used as the counter and reference electrode, respectively. The
120 electrochemical tests were performed in a three-electrode undivided glass cell reactor with
121 continuous stirring and purging (He). Inline gaseous product analysis was achieved by gas
122 chromatography (G.C.) equipped with flame ionisation (FID) and thermal conductivity

123 detector (TCD) . Hydrocarbons (C1-C4) were detected FID using a RTX-1 column (15 m L*
124 0.32 mm I.D, 5 μ m fused silica film thickness at 45°C). Light gases (H₂, O₂ and CO₂) were
125 detected C TCD coupled with a Carboxen® 1010 column (15m L* 0.32 mm ID at 70°C).
126 External calibration was carried out for CH₄, C₂H₄, CH₆, H₂, O₂, and CO₂ with $r^2 > 0.995$.
127 Gaseous products from the reactor headspace were collected continuously using He purging
128 (30ml/min). Liquid products (CH₃OH, C₃H₆O₂) were collected at the end of the experiment in
129 aliquots and analysed by headspace GC-FID (Agilent) using a Zebron 7HG-G013-11 (0.25 μ m
130 ID, 250 μ m, 40 m) column for product separation. The aqueous phase pyrolysis was analysed
131 by the GC-MS (7890A MS 5975C – Agilent Technologies). Prior to the analysis, the pyrolysis
132 oil was diluted 20 times with acetone and acetone-soluble compounds were extracted and
133 filtered before injection. The GC-MS data were analysed and compared with the pyrolysis oil
134 component database present in the lab.

135 Liquid analysis of the aqueous fraction of the pyrolysis oil before and after analysis was carried
136 out using 1D 13C and 2D HSQC(¹H-¹³C) NMR (400 MHz Bruker). Prior to the measurement,
137 150 mg of the liquid sample was dissolved in 0.7 ml dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)-d₆ solvent
138 and subsequently filtered. NMR spectra were processed through MestReNova v14.1. Raman
139 analysis was performed using a home-build Raman spectrometer equipped with 630 nm
140 excitation laser source. Measurements were acquired at 35 mW, 150 ms and 50 kHz.

141 Prior to electrolysis, the electrochemical cell and electrode holders were cleaned with ethanol,
142 boiled and sonicated three times in Milli-Q water (18.2 Ω). Voltammetry were performed at a
143 sweep rate of 100 mV/sec and corrected for the ohmic drop determined by the current
144 interruption (CI) method. Chronopotentiometry at 25 mA/cm² at room temperature and
145 pressure was used to convert the aqueous phase or model compounds, respectively. All
146 experiments were carried out at a 600 rpm stirring rate, and pH was monitored before and after
147 the experiment. Potentials are converted to the RHE scale and the F.E was calculated by
148 $FE = (nFZ)/(Q)$; where n is the number of moles of the specific product, F is the Faraday
149 constant, z is the number of electrons, and Q is the charge passed in coulombs.

150 **03.Results and Discussions**

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152 **3.1 Model compound electrooxidation**

153 Kolbe oxidation of acetic acid/acetate electrolytes (pH 5) was first investigated by cyclic
154 voltammetry (CV) in an undivided three-electrode cell, using both Pt and BDD as working

155 electrode (see Figure1). For platinum electrodes, the platinum oxide formation is observed to
156 occur in the potential range between 0.9-1.2 V_{RHE} , subsequently leading to a rise in current
157 at $\sim 1.6 V_{RHE}$ for water oxidation and likely competing acid discharge. After reaching the so-
158 called inflection zone acetate discharge is considered to be dominant, thereby suppressing the
159 OER, leading to methyl radical formation¹⁵.

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161 *Figure 1 Cyclic voltammetry of Pt and BDD electrodes in 1M acetic acid/sodium acetate at pH 5*

162 The transition point between OER prevailing currents to Kolbe electrolysis lies at $\sim 2.5 V_{RHE}$,
163 as confirmed by RRDE investigations, that show diminishing OER currents at $2.5 V_{RHE}$ (data
164 not shown). Due to the abundance of methyl radicals, dimerization is a favourable pathway
165 forming ethane as the primary product. The high current density with potential sweep also
166 indicates that the Kolbe reaction is surface-specific and occurs via direct electron transfer.

167 In Figure 1, the characteristic CV obtained with BDD in acetate solution shows no change in
168 electrochemical response below $2.6 V_{RHE}$ indicating that acetic acid is not oxidised before the
169 onset of water oxidation¹⁶. The absence of a pseudo-plateau region, i.e. the inflection zone
170 observed for Pt electrodes, suggests that oxidation occurs via an indirect mechanism rather than
171 the direct electron transfer on the BDD surface.

172 Due to the larger overpotential for OER on BDD, the simultaneous water discharge leads to
173 the formation of weakly adsorbing OH^- radicals. The reaction between methyl and OH^- radical
174 directing to a different reaction pathway¹⁷, i.e. methanol formation. Another possibility of
175 acetate conversion to methanol is the Hofer Moest reaction^{17,18}, in which alkyl radical oxidized

176 further to the carbocation which reactions with OH anion and methanol formation takes place,
177 as shown in the Figure 10¹⁵.

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Figure 1 Reaction Mechanism of acetic acid electrooxidation on electrode

192 To reveal the reaction selectivity and product formation rates, chronopotentiometry was used
193 at 25 mA/cm² for one hour. The product formation rate is shown in Figure 3 for the Pt electrode
194 and Figure 4 for the BDD electrode. The Kolbe product ethane was formed continuously at a
195 significant production rate of $\sim 7 \mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{cm}^2$ at Pt electrodes contrasting the negligible
196 methane and ethylene production rates. The production rate of CO₂, which is the intermediate
197 of acid decarboxylation, reaches twice the rate of ethane formation in agreement with the
198 proposed Kolbe reaction pathway. H₂ is the product evolving at the cathode. Concerning the
199 F.E, the reaction is more selective towards Kolbe products formation, with 92.6 % FE to ethane
200 and 1.84% FE to OER over the entire time range. It shows that the Kolbe reaction dominates
201 the OER already at low current density of 25 mA/cm². The liquid samples show no Hofer
202 Moest product, which can give us information that the complete coverage of the acetate layer
203 on PtO-Pt inhibits the overoxidation of methyl radical to carbenium ion.

204 For BDD, the production rate of products and FE differs significantly and carbon dioxide and
205 cathodically produced hydrogen are the only detectable gas phase products. Considering the
206 difficulties arising from online liquid product quantification, the production rate of methanol
207 and methyl acetate are only obtained after electrolysis. The methanol and methyl acetate

208 production rates obtained, i.e. of 6.3 and 1.2 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{cm}^2$, closely resembling the production
 209 rate of ethane observed on Pt electrodes. This is also reflected in the FE in Figure 5, showing
 210 that the decarboxylation reaction is selective to Hofer Moest and non-Kolbe products.

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 212 *Figure 3 Production rate of products from 1M acetate solution at pH 5 on Pt electrode at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour*

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Figure 4 Production rate of products from 1M acetate solution at pH 5 on BDD electrode at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour

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 215 The significant difference in CO₂ production rate with almost double CO₂ evolution compared
 216 to ethane on Pt electrodes contrasts the close to equimolar ratio of CO₂ and methanol observed

217 for BDD. This is justifiable by the difference in reaction mechanism. BDD is known to corrode
 218 in the presence of methyl radical, and the corrosion could lead to graphitisation of the BDD
 219 surface²⁰. Upon subjecting the electrode to a high oxidation potential, graphite carbon
 220 degradation can also contribute to the CO₂ content in the gas product streams and thus ongoing
 221 efforts are focusing on disentangling CO₂ contributions.

222
 223 *Figure 5 Average faradaic efficiency of anodic reaction products (Kolbe, Hofer Moest and OER) and the acetate oxidation*
 224 *rate on Pt and BDD at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour*

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 226 **3.2 Aqueous phase pyrolysis oil electrooxidation**

227 Cyclic voltammetry using aqueous phase pyrolysis with Pt and BDD working electrodes
 228 revealed that half-cell potentials larger than 2.5 V are required to observe oxidative currents as
 229 shown in Figure 6. This is in good agreement with the data presented for the model compound
 230 acetic acid. However, the current densities are lower which could be due to the passivation of
 231 the electrode surface by pyrolysis oil compounds and char causing rise in the resistance near
 232 the electrode surface.

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Figure 6 CV of BDD and Pt in aqueous phase pyrolysis oil at pH5

235 Pyrolysis oil is a complex mixture of chemical compounds, and its complete analysis with GC-
 236 MS is cumbersome. Nevertheless, GC-MS analysis of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil confirms
 237 the presence of carboxylic acid, furfural, phenolic and sugar compounds. Cyclopentenone and
 238 1-hydroxy-2-propanone are ketones, and furfural is a furan product followed by anhydrase
 239 mannopyranose, which originates from biomass cellulose. Though, qualitative results about the
 240 significant fraction can be obtained, the overlap of compounds due to their similar m/z ratios,
 241 renders it difficult to obtain an unambiguous assignment and additional analytics are thus
 242 required.

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Figure 7 GC-MS spectra of aqueous fraction of pyrolysis oil before electrolysis

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Table 1 Retention time of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil analysis by GC-MS

Retention time	Component
5.4-5.8	1-propanol
5.8-7.5	Hydrazine carboxylic acid
8-8.1	Acetic acid

8.1-8.2	Formic acid methyl ester
9.1-10	1-hydroxy-2-propanone
15.9-16.7	butanediol
16.8-16.9	Cyclopentenone
17	Furfural
17.6-17.8	Diacetone from solvent
27.3-27.6	2-hydroxy 3 methyl cyclopent-1-one
29.8-30.33	Guaiacol
34.5-35.2	4-methyl guaiacol
55.9-56.9	Anhydrose mannopyranose

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248 To further explore the composition of treated and untreated pyrolysis oil, we used Raman
 249 spectroscopy and NMR. The Raman spectra of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil before and after
 250 electrolysis are shown in Figure 2, featuring the different functionalities of the organic
 251 compounds. Correlation of Raman wavenumbers' with different bonds and functional groups
 252 has been obtained using literature data^{21,22}. For untreated oils the most prominent features occur
 253 between 800 cm⁻¹ to 1700 cm⁻¹ exhibiting the vibrations of C-O, C-H, C=C and C=O bonds,
 254 respectively. The stretching vibration intensity at 1630 cm⁻¹ is only slightly altered showing
 255 that unsaturated C=C components present in pyrolysis oil is almost unaffected by electrolysis.
 256 In the regions of 2850 to 2956 cm⁻¹, the bands attribute to methyl and methylene groups are
 257 observed with no significant difference irrespectively of the electrode used for treatment.

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Figure 8 Raman spectra of pyrolysis oil aqueous fraction before and after electrolysis with platinum and boron-doped diamond anodes

261 The intensity of C-C stretching vibration is more prominent for pyrolysis oil treated with Pt
262 than BDD electrodes. In all the samples, the ester carbonyl vibration is not visible at 1746 cm⁻¹,
263 indicating the absence of the ester product obtained by (non)Kolbe reaction. A likely
264 explanation is the degradation of esters to alcohols and acids²³ caused by hydrolysis. The
265 Raman signals intensity increased for the pyrolysis oil after electrolysis for C-O, C-H and C=C
266 bonds. Though the carbonyl group vibration of fatty acids was not observed its presence was
267 confirmed in GCMS analysis. The carbonyl band determination is much more favourable
268 through FTIR because of its shift to lower wavenumbers. Although, clear changes are observe
269 by Raman spectroscopy it is difficult to quantify. Specifically florescence cannot be neglected
270 causing analysis challenging.

271 **3.2.1 NMR analysis of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil**

272 The ¹³C NMR of aqueous pyrolysis oil before and after electrolysis at 25 mA/cm² performed
273 for 60 minutes is depicted in Figure 9. The chemical shift can be assigned to the various
274 functional groups. As such in the chemical shift of 0-55ppm, the short, long and branched
275 aliphatic compounds appear. The sharp solvent peak of DMSO-d₆ is located at 40 ppm. It can
276 be seen that there is a rise in aliphatic compounds after pyrolysis oil electrolysis independent
277 of the electrode used. In the range of 55-95ppm, alcohols, ethers, phenolics, methoxy, and
278 carbohydrates are present. Clearly within this region it can be observed that multiple signals
279 increase in intensity and additional signals appear after electrolysis. From GC-MS data, we
280 found the presence of phenolics and carbohydrate sugars in the aqueous phase of pyrolysis oil
281 and can thus tentatively assign these peaks to alcohols and ethers obtained as products of
282 (non)Kolbe and Hofer Moest's reaction. Aromatic olefins should appear with a chemical shift
283 of 95-166.5 ppm. However, there was no significant peak present. The lack of aromatics is also
284 revealed by GC-MS analysis. The absence of olefins before and after electrolysis is likely
285 related to the insolubility of aromatics in water.²⁴

286 In the range 166.5-180 ppm, carboxylic acids and esters appear. There is a rise of the peak,
287 which is probably related to the ester formation after electrolysis due to Kolbe electrolysis. In
288 the region of 180-220 ppm, aldehydes and ketones appear but seem to be unaffected by the
289 treatment. Ketones are known to be resistant to oxidation because of the absence of hydrogen
290 atoms attached to carbonyl. So the little increment in the region could be related to other
291 oxidation reactions that yield ketones and aldehydes.

292 The percentages of functional groups can be calculated based on the assumption that all carbon
293 functionalities are detected and integrated (see Figure 10). The quantitative analysis shows no
294 significant variation in the aliphatic C-C group. After electrolysis on both Pt and BDD, the
295 methoxy group disappeared. Moreover, aliphatic C-O groups with increasing C% for pyrolysis
296 oil after electrolysis on BDD and Pt increase to 67% and 66%, respectively. The change is
297 probably related to the formation of alcohols by (non)Kolbe and Hofer Moest reaction, which
298 gives rise to an aliphatic C-O group. The higher proportion of aliphatic C-O on BDD indicates
299 the selectivity to the alcohol group. For the aromatic C-H group, the carbon percentage
300 decreased after electrolysis showing that it is susceptible to electrooxidation. As it is shown by
301 GC-MS that mono phenolic compounds (guaiacol) were present in raw pyrolysis oil, that are
302 known to be prone to oxidation, supplements the information from our analysis²⁵.

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Figure 9 ¹³C NMR of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil before and after electrolysis on Pt and BDD anode at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour

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Figure 10 ^{13}C NMR integrated area for specific carbon for specific functional group before and after electrolysis

308 With 1D NMR, there is the advantage of simplicity for sample preparation and less sensitivity
 309 to water as compared to other methods (FTIR). Still, the significant overlap in C-C and C-H
 310 aromatics chemical shift requires additional product analysis²⁶. The use of 2D-NMR is still
 311 rarely reported for the analysis of pyrolysis oil in the context of electrooxidation but can
 312 provide insights into functional groups regardless of their molecular weight. The HSQC spectra
 313 (see Figure 11) of pyrolysis oil are segregated into three zones. The top zone relates to aliphatic
 314 C-H bonds; the oxygenates present in the middle and aromatic C-H bonds in the bottom. It can
 315 be noticed that aromatic C-H bond compounds are not visible, confirming the absence of
 316 aromatics after aqueous phase extraction. The oxygenate fraction dominates in the aqueous
 317 phase of pyrolysis oil before electrolysis, but its intensity decreased after electrolysis on BDD
 318 and Pt. The oxygenated region appeared crowded with alcohols and ethers fractions in the range
 319 of ^1H 3.5-5.0 ppm and ^{13}C 50-80 ppm.

320 The strong peak in the contour region at the chemical shift of ^1H 3.00-3.7 ppm and ^{13}C 50-72.5
 321 ppm shows the presence of methyl groups bounded to alcohol, ester or ether. The primary
 322 alcohol are located at ^1H 3.4 and ^{13}C 60.3 ppm. The signal location is correlated using literature
 323 ²⁷⁻²⁹. It can be seen in Figure 12 that the strong signal of a primary alcohol, which appears at
 324 ^1H 3.42 ppm and ^{13}C 60.3 ppm in the electrolysis with BDD sample, shows the increase of
 325 alcohol functionalities compared with the untreated oil. The carboxylic acid groups can be seen
 326 at ^1H 4.1 ppm and ^{13}C 70 ppm. The lower abundance of acids after electrolysis confirms their
 327 electrooxidation. Importantly, the carbonyl function in the range of 3.1-3.4 ppm and 70-80 ppm

328 disappears after electrolysis with BDD but remains similar when Pt electrodes are used. It is
329 suggested that aldehydes are prone to oxidation and can easily be converted to carboxylic acids.

330 In the aliphatic region, it can be seen that branched alkanes are reduced after electrolysis with
331 platinum. The overall aliphatic spectrum for BDD-treated pyrolysis oil and raw aqueous phase
332 oil remains the same, showing that aliphatic compounds are not prone to oxidation at BDD
333 electrodes.

334 Despite the first trends observed additional comparison of the data is require. Specifically
335 oxygenate functionalities and other yet unidentified compounds must be assigned and
336 quantified.

Figure 11 2D- HSQC NMR of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil before electrolysis

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369 *Figure 12 2D HSQC NMR of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil after electrolysis on BDD at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour*

386 *Figure 13 2D HSQC NMR of aqueous phase pyrolysis oil after electrolysis on BDD at 25mA/cm² for 1 hour*

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388 **Challenges in electrochemical conversion of pyrolysis oil**

389 In this contribution a first overview of the complex reactant and product spectrum of aqueous
390 phase pyrolysis oil was presented clearly revealing the differences in product distribution
391 between the electrode materials used for electrooxidation. Though this is in agreement with the
392 model compound analysis, several challenges are to be tackled to fully resolve and utilize direct
393 electrochemical conversion of pyrolysis oil. As such prolonged electrolysis experiments
394 resulting in more significant differences in the functional groups before and after electrolysis
395 are required and will be addressed in future work.

396 In addition to the challenges faced with the aqueous phase of pyrolysis oil, the use of pure
397 pyrolysis oil will cause additional challenges. In general pyrolysis oil is a very thick and
398 viscous liquid and cannot be used without pre-treatment in electrochemical cells. The viscosity
399 will cause hindrance in the flow of the oil across the electrode and poisons the active sites of
400 electrocatalytic material. The highly acidic pH of oil $> \text{pH } 2$ and its conductivity are obstacles
401 to be overcome and hinder the commercialisation of its application³⁰. The complexity of
402 pyrolysis oil due to hundreds of compounds, its composition variation due to different
403 feedstock and the ageing process can lead to non-standard irreproducible experimental
404 investigation. The analysis of oil is highly complex and requires multiple techniques, GC,
405 GCMS, FTIR, Raman, LCMS, NMR, and FT-ICR among others are needed to supplement the
406 product composition. The complexity can be reduced using the aqueous fraction of pyrolysis
407 oil (water soluble). Still the better approach is to fractionate the pyrolysis oil, extract carboxylic
408 acids to increase the pH, and extract sugars to reduce the polymerisation probability. Our model
409 compound analysis revealed that carboxylic acids can be converted through electrochemical
410 decarboxylation into alkanes and alcohols, simultaneously providing the protons and electrons
411 for the electrochemical hydrogenation of pyrolysis oil. In short, the complex analysis of
412 pyrolysis oil before and after electrolysis and concluded that acid separation would be
413 advantageous for any process.

414

415 **4. Conclusion**

416 Anodic upgradation of pyrolysis oil can enhance pyrolysis oil quality. The aqueous fraction
417 contains mostly soluble acids and sugars and can be used for electrochemical upgradation.
418 Using model compounds we show that ethane can be produced electrochemically with a Pt
419 electrode at $\sim 90\%$ FE, while methanol can be produced at 82.2% FE. The high current

420 efficiencies of model compounds electrooxidation show that selective oxidation is possible.
421 However, using pyrolysis oil as a standalone mixture is very challenging. The complex
422 analytics of components was tackled with multiple methods. Specifically using ¹³C NMR
423 including quantitative analysis we estimated the percentage of each functional group before
424 and after electrolysis. In addition we used 2D NMR, a semi-quantitative technique, to obtain
425 insight into compounds' abundance regardless of their molecular weight and revealed that
426 aromatic C-H fraction decrease while the aliphatic C-O fraction increased. The area of
427 oxygenates decreases after electrolysis showing the deoxygenation is likely happened which
428 indicates the upgradation of pyrolysis oil.

429 We conclude that the separation of the acidic fraction is likely needed to use carboxylic acids
430 from the pyrolysis oil for electrolysis. It is still a question of how the reaction's selectivity
431 changes with increasing model mixtures' complexity. The energy efficiency of the pyrolysis
432 oil electrolysis, economic factors, electrolyser design, high current density, and acids
433 separation process will be addressed in future.

434

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